

Abstract

Ocean chemistry and carbonate sedimentation link Earth’s climate, carbon cycle, and marine pH . The carbonate system in seawater is complex and there are large uncertainties in key parameters in deep time. Here we link sedimentary textures formed in arid coastal environments and preserved in the rock record to past seawater carbonate chemistry. Our modeling shows that the global and temporal abundance of tepee structures and pisoids—features associated with evaporitic peritidal environments—is correlated with secular shifts in marine alkalinity and saturation state for carbonate minerals. Tepee structures and pisoids co-vary with available shelf area during the Paleozoic and early Mesozoic, consistent with supercontinent cycles exerting primary control on alkalinity and saturation state. Tepee structures and pisoids become scarce after the mid-Jurassic, when the expansion of pelagic calcifiers and the breakup of Pangea permanently alter marine carbonate chemistry. As independent sedimentary proxies, tepees and pisoids serve as benchmarks for global carbon cycle models and provide a new proxy record of seawater chemistry that can help discern links among tectonics, biotic innovation, and seawater chemistry.

Plain Language Summary

Sedimentary rocks tell us that Earth’s oceans and atmosphere have changed through time. Changes in the carbon cycle—the movement of carbon between Earth’s interior and surface, including its distribution within oceans, atmospheres, and biological material—is important because it connects Earth’s climate, oceans, life and surface environments. Here we present a new method for tracking carbon cycle changes based on textures in carbonate rocks. Certain textures were more common in hot, salty coastal areas up until 170 million years ago. Changes in the sedimentary record coincide with the appearance of tiny new organisms that build carbonate skeletons. Our data from non-skeletal carbonates support the idea that this evolutionary event substantially changed ocean chemistry. We also outline how these proxies might be used to test the co-evolution of life and Earth’s surface in deep time.

1 Introduction

Carbonate rocks are physical products of Earth’s carbon cycle. Carbonate burial regulates both global climate and marine pH by removing atmospheric CO_2 through silicate weathering (Berner et al., 1983; Urey, 1952). Carbonate precipitation depends on the carbonate chemistry of seawater, a system with two degrees of freedom among six variables: pCO_2 [bars], HCO_3^- [mmol/kgw], CO_3^{2-} [mmol/kgw], pH , total carbon [mmol/kgw], and alkalinity [mmol/kgw] (Zeebe & Wolf-Gladrow, 2001). The CO_3^{2-} concentration is usually depicted in a related quantity, the saturation state Ω , for either calcite or aragonite:

$$\Omega = \frac{\gamma[Ca^{2+}]\gamma[CO_3^{2-}]}{K_{sp}} \quad (1)$$

where γ is the activity of dissolved ions, brackets denote concentrations, and K_{sp} is a thermodynamic solubility constant of the mineral. Sedimentological or geochemical observations that constrain two variables—and thus solve the system completely—are fundamental to several cross-disciplinary problems. Constraints on Precambrian pH and pCO_2 are important for understanding how Earth maintained liquid water when solar luminosity was lower than today (Grotzinger & Kasting, 1993; Blättler et al., 2017). In the Phanerozoic, rapid changes in Ω help explain the correlation between mass extinctions and carbon cycle perturbations (Payne & Kump, 2007; Kiessling & Simpson, 2011).

63 The search for at least two independent proxies to constrain the carbonate system
 64 has proven challenging beyond the Cenozoic. Of the six variables, only atmospheric $p\text{CO}_2$
 65 is moderately well-constrained for the Phanerozoic (e.g., Royer, 2006; Foster et al., 2017),
 66 but it has larger uncertainties in the Precambrian (Grotzinger & Kasting, 1993; Blättler
 67 et al., 2017). Surface Ω can be calculated by tracking the calcite compensation depth
 68 (Pälike et al., 2012; Tyrrell & Zeebe, 2004) but subduction of oceanic lithosphere lim-
 69 its these records beyond the Jurassic. A $p\text{H}$ proxy using boron isotopes ($\delta^{11}\text{B}$) has been
 70 developed but is challenging to interpret over timescales longer than the residence time
 71 of boron in seawater (i.e. 14-20 my, Pagani et al., 2005). These challenges are compounded
 72 because Earth’s carbon cycle was probably re-organized during a radiation of pelagic cal-
 73 cifiers known as the Mid-Mesozoic Revolution (Zeebe & Westbroek, 2003; Grotzinger &
 74 Knoll, 1995). Prior to this event, alkalinity and Ω could have been many times higher
 75 than present because of weaker export of carbonate into the deep ocean. Several Earth
 76 systems models offer testable hypotheses provided appropriate proxies can be found (Arvidson
 77 et al., 2006; Ridgwell, 2005; Zeebe et al., 2012).

78 Arguably the most useful evidence for ancient ocean chemistry comes from phys-
 79 ical textures (e.g., the presence, size, and morphology of grains and sedimentary struc-
 80 tures) in non-skeletal carbonates and evaporites. Recent efforts have focused on com-
 81 bining sedimentological data with geochemical modeling to quantify these proxies. For
 82 example, an Ω proxy based on the size of coated grains such as ooids (Trower et al., 2017)
 83 has been applied to questions about Neoproterozoic climate (Trower, 2020). Other ap-
 84 proaches have been developed based on carbonate textures and accessory minerals in large
 85 evaporite basins (Pope et al., 2000); however, a drawback of this approach is that large
 86 evaporite basins are unevenly distributed in the rock record (Babel & Schreiber, 2014).
 87 Here we hypothesize that textures in coastal evaporitic systems are also sensitive to sec-
 88 ular changes in carbonate chemistry and can provide a high resolution record. To test
 89 this hypothesis, we compiled data from Phanerozoic arid coastal deposits and tested for
 90 secular trends in two common facies: tepee structures and pisoids. Since tepees and pisoids
 91 are associated with rapid carbonate precipitation, we used box models to investigate whether
 92 proposed changes in Phanerozoic ocean chemistry, especially alkalinity and Ω , matched
 93 trends in facies abundance. Our results provide insights into the Phanerozoic carbon cy-
 94 cle and a stepping stone toward understanding the Precambrian record of Earth’s atmo-
 95 sphere and oceans.

96 1.1 Modern versus ancient arid coastal settings

97 In arid coastal settings—e.g., sabkhas, salinas, and saline lakes (Yechieli & Wood,
 98 2002)—evaporating seawater creates distinctive sedimentary features known as tepee struc-
 99 tures and marine pisoids. Tepee structures form when carbonate cements precipitate in
 100 porewaters with little overburden. The force of crystallization exerts enough pressure
 101 that near-surface crusts expand upwards and break. Tepee structures appear as dish-
 102 shaped polygons along bedding planes or as broken antiforms with abundant cements
 103 in cross-section (Assereto & Kendall, 1977; Kendall & Warren, 1987) (Fig. 1a). Beds above
 104 tepee structures often thin and onlap these features, differentiating them from later struc-
 105 tural deformation. Marine pisoids are large (>2 millimeter) coated grains that often ac-
 106 cumulate near tepee structures, especially in inter-tepee depressions (Esteban & Pray,
 107 1983). Although the term ‘pisoid’ usually refers to authigenic features in soil caliches,
 108 here we use the term to denote allochems from arid coastal environments (Assereto &
 109 Folk, 1976; Esteban & Pray, 1983). Pisoids in these settings often have textures and minerol-
 110 ogy (i.e., aragonite) that preclude a meteoric origin (Loucks & Folk, 1976).

111 Tepees and pisoids from modern coastal settings are imperfect analogs for ancient
 112 deposits. Modern tepees are smaller and have poorer preservation potential compared
 113 to their ancient counterparts. Although polygonal crusts formed by early cements have
 114 long been recognized from arid coastlines near Abu Dhabi (Shinn, 1969), mapping by

Figure 1. Middle Permian arid coastal facies from the Delaware Basin, USA. (a) Characteristic cross-section through a tepee structure. (b) Centimeter-scale pisoids with relatively even laminations and broken grains indicating transport and reworking. The scale and preservation of these facies is unprecedented among Holocene analogs. Line tracings highlight geometries in both figures

115 Lokier and Steuber (2009) showed that active tepee structures were easily eroded and
 116 comprised less than 2% of polygon borders. Subsequent trenching by Court et al. (2017)
 117 revealed that tepees were unlikely to survive even shallow burial. These results are per-
 118 plexing because many ancient tepees formed topographically high, wave-resistant bar-
 119 rier islands (Esteban & Pray, 1983). Pisoids are equally problematic; modern analogs
 120 precipitate in marine-derived, caliche-like crusts (Scholle & Kinsman, 1974) but ancient
 121 examples display internal breaks suggesting sediment transport as loose grains (Esteban
 122 & Pray, 1983) (Fig. 1b). Many ancient tepees and pisoids are also very large compared
 123 to their modern counterparts, with tepee structures displaying meter-scale synoptic re-
 124 lief and pisoids measuring several centimeters across (Fig. 1). The small size and poor
 125 preservation of Holocene examples raises questions as to whether ancient examples formed
 126 under distinctly different environmental conditions.

127 2 Data and Methods

128 2.1 Database of sedimentary features

129 To test the idea that tepee-pisoid facies were more abundant in the past, we con-
 130 structed a database of 242 documented Phanerozoic arid coastal carbonate deposits. Each
 131 deposit was binned by series/epoch and all stages and epochs were converted to the equiv-
 132 alent designation in the 2018 International Chronostratigraphic Chart (Cohen et al., 2018).
 133 Database entries were collected using from Google Scholar’s full text search using terms
 134 related to arid coastal deposits: ‘birdseye,’ ‘fenestral/fenestrae,’ ‘mud cracks,’ ‘algal lam-
 135 inations,’ ‘microbial laminations,’ ‘supratidal,’ ‘intertidal,’ ‘peritidal,’ and ‘sabkha.’ We
 136 prioritized sites with evidence for evaporitic conditions within the section (*in situ* gyp-
 137 sum, anhydrite, celestite, or halite), evaporite molds or pseudomorphs (e.g., some occurrences

Figure 2. Setup for evaporation box models. (a) Aragonite saturation states calculated from modern sabkha data (see SI). Median values (bold lines) are higher for surface water samples than porewater samples. The grey box highlights the range of aragonite Ω values for unevaporated tropical seawater (Jiang et al., 2015). (b) Schematic cross section through arid intertidal and supratidal environments. (c) Box model setup for surface water rapidly exchanged with the ocean. (d) Box model setup for evaporation from the water table. Note that the direction of the fluxes (vertical or horizontal) has no bearing on the model.

138 of length slow chalcedony), or breccias interpreted as the result of syn- or post-depositional
 139 evaporite dissolution. We removed examples from non-marine environments such as lakes,
 140 playas, and continental sabkhas. Geochemical evidence, if present, had to be consistent
 141 with marine water sources. Deep-water or basin-centered evaporites were not considered.

142 Because ‘tepee’ and ‘pisoid’ are non-genetic terms, we assessed if these features had
 143 non-marine origins and discarded those that did. For tepees, deposits were ineligible if
 144 1) tepees were ‘pseudo-anticlines’ associated with paleosol formation and caliche precipi-
 145 tation; 2) the host phase was another evaporite mineral (e.g., sulfates or halite) rather
 146 than a carbonate mineral; 3) the structure was unrelated to evaporites in general, e.g.,
 147 associated with methane seeps or fluid-escape structures; 4) the tepees lacked features
 148 such as sheet crack cements, brecciated cores, and overthrust limbs, all evidence of space
 149 created by layer-parallel expansion; 5) the examples were <10 cm in height (‘micro-tepees’)
 150 as these were difficult to classify from photos. For pisoids, deposits were ineligible if the
 151 grains were associated with paleosol formation (circumgranular cracks, aveolar structures,
 152 etc.), cave pearls, travertine deposits, or other characteristics indicating a meteoric ori-
 153 gin (Scholle & Ulmer-Scholle, 2003; Swineford et al., 1958).

154 Deposits within each time slice were plotted spatially in Google Earth with an *ad*
 155 *hoc* limit of two database entries per a $5 \times 5^\circ$ latitude/longitude rectangle. This constraint
 156 reduced bias towards a small number of well-published sites such as the Middle Permian
 157 of West Texas, the Triassic of Italy, and the Jurassic of Morocco. Additionally, we chose
 158 to count published occurrences rather than total thickness or the areal extent of deposits
 159 (e.g., Peters et al., 2018) because tepees and pisoids were often described in the text but
 160 were not finely resolved on stratigraphic columns. Results were pooled into four time pe-
 161 riods with similar characteristics for statistical testing: 1) Cambrian–Devonian, 2) Car-
 162 boniferous–Early Permian, 3) Middle Permian–Early Jurassic, and 4) Middle Jurassic–present.
 163 We used Fisher’s exact test of independence (Fisher, 1992) instead of a Chi-squared test
 164 because there were <1000 observations (McDonald, 2009). A *post-hoc* pairwise Fisher
 165 comparison was conducted among groups, with the resulting p-values adjusted for mul-

Table 1. Variables used for evaporation box models. Sources are 1–Demicco et al. (2005), 2–Ridgwell (2005), and 3–Zhong and Mucci (1989).

Name	Type	Average	Range	Units	Source
Na ⁺	variable	449.1	407.8-488.5	[mmol/kgw]	1
Mg ²⁺	variable	40.8	32.8-55.1	[mmol/kgw]	1
SO ₄ ²⁻	variable	15.8	9.9-28	[mmol/kgw]	1
$\Omega_{calcite}$	variable	6.6	5.1-10.7	[-]	2
Alkalinity	variable	4.0	1.8-7.9	[mmol/kgw]	2
n	constant	3.12	[N/A]	[-]	3
k	constant	0.312	[N/A]	[μ mol/m ² hr]	3

166 tiple comparisons using the Holm method (Holm, 1979) and the result rendered as a com-
 167 pact letter display.

168 The database approach relies on several key assumptions. The first is that the te-
 169 pees and pisoids are correlated with the rate of carbonate precipitation at each site. Higher
 170 rates should lead to tepee structures that are larger and more resistant to weathering,
 171 and thus have greater preservation potential in the rock record. For pisoids, we consid-
 172 ered recent work on ooids showing that size represents surface-normal precipitation bal-
 173 anced by abrasion during transport (Trower et al., 2017). However, well-preserved crys-
 174 tal terminations (Loucks & Folk, 1976) and large particle sizes suggest that abrasion is
 175 relatively infrequent for pisoids, suggesting that precipitation rate is the primary con-
 176 trol on pisoid size. Greater precipitation rates should result in larger equilibrium grain
 177 sizes that are more likely to cross the two-millimeter diameter cutoff to be classified as
 178 ‘pisoids’ in the literature.

179 2.2 Geochemical models of seawater evaporation

180 Geochemical models of evaporating seawater were used as a quantitative aid for
 181 interpreting facies trends through time. Chemical data from modern brines were com-
 182 piled so that mineral saturation states could be calculated (Banat et al., 2005; Rivers
 183 et al., 2019; Basyoni & Mousa, 2009; Basyoni & Aref, 2015; Wood et al., 2005; Levy, 1977;
 184 Wood et al., 2002) with an emphasis on marine brines rather than continental ones (cf.
 185 Wood et al., 2005). We also constructed simple box models of evaporitic systems to com-
 186 pute steady-state Ω values through the Phanerozoic by imposing Phanerozoic-scale changes
 187 in temperature, carbonate chemistry, and major ion composition. Estimates of Phanero-
 188 zoic marine chemistry are compiled from several sources (Table 1): carbonate variables
 189 were taken from Ridgwell (2005), calcium from Stanley and Hardie (1998), and all other
 190 major ions were either taken from Demicco et al. (2005) or held at modern values if es-
 191 timates were unavailable. A range of temperatures (30-50°C) were tested based on tem-
 192 peratures in tidal flats near Abu Dhabi (Wood et al., 2005; Lokier & Steuber, 2009). Val-
 193 ues were binned in 20 myr intervals from 550 Ma to present. Activities and mineral sat-
 194 uration states were solved with PHREEQC (Parkhurst & Appelo, 2013) using the Pitzer
 195 database (Plummer, 1988; Appelo, 2015). The Pitzer ion interaction model (Pitzer, 1973)
 196 is well-suited for calculating ion activity in brines and has been used extensively in stud-
 197 ies of both modern and ancient evaporite systems (Wood & Sanford, 1990; Sanford &
 198 Wood, 1991; Wood et al., 2005; Blättler et al., 2017).

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2.3 Box models

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The box modeling approach closely follows the open system evaporite models of Wood and Sanford (1990) and Sanford and Wood (1991). The water balance in an arbitrary control volume, V_0 , is given by:

$$Q_i = Q_o + Q_e \quad (2)$$

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$$Q_o = fQ_i \quad (3)$$

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where Q_i [kg/s] is the flux into the volume, Q_o [kg/s] is non-evaporative flux out of the system (e.g., tidal exchange or density-driven reflux), and Q_e [kg/s] is flux from evaporation. The fraction of total outgoing fluxes between evaporative and non-evaporative losses is designated by parameter f , where $0 < f < 1$.

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The balance for solute species C is:

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = Q_i C_i - Q_o C_o - P \quad (4)$$

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where C_i [kg/s] and C_o [kg/s] are the solute concentrations for fluid inflow and outflow, respectively, and P [kg/s] is the removal rate of solute by mineral precipitation. If salinity is roughly conservative—that is $P \approx 0$ because sulfate minerals and halite do not precipitate—the ratio of fluxes corresponds to a unique salinity, S_0 [$kg\ solute/kg\ water$], at steady state:

$$S_o = \frac{Q_i}{Q_o} S_i = \frac{1}{f} S_i \quad (5)$$

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We chose a salinity of $S \approx 47$ ppt ($f = 0.75$) as this is well within the range of modern tidal pools in Abu Dhabi (Lokier & Steuber, 2009). To avoid dealing with absolute timescales, we replaced time variables with total volumes of fluid pushed through the control volume (V/V_0) following the convention of Wood and Sanford (1990) and Sanford and Wood (1991).

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Based on data from modern environments, we built two endmember models dubbed the surface water-kinetic model and the porewater-equilibrium model (Fig. 2). The surface water-kinetic model represents surface environments where the residence time of water is short enough that carbonate precipitation does not meaningfully affect the fluid composition (Fig 2b,c). Under this scenario, the precipitation term, P , can be neglected from the solute balance and steady-state alkalinity and Ω are maintained by outflow rather than mineral precipitation. The accumulation of (volumetrically minor) precipitates follows a kinetic rate law:

$$P = k(\Omega_{ss} - 1)^n \quad (6)$$

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where P is the precipitation rate [$moles/(hr \cdot m^2)$], Ω_{ss} is the steady-state carbonate saturation state, and k and n are empirical constants (see SI). The surface water-kinetic model yields steady-state saturation states that are higher than those in the parent water, reflecting the high saturation states in modern coastal embayments and tidal pools (Fig 2a). The porewater-equilibrium endmember model represents pore fluids with residence times longer than the timescale for kinetic precipitation rates (Fig 2d). Under these conditions, steady-state variables represent a dynamic equilibrium between outflow and mineral precipitation. This is simulated using the EQUILIBRIUM_PHASES command in PHREEQC which removes excess ions until $\Omega = 1$. This model simulates the low saturation states found in tidal-flat porewaters (Fig. 2a). For each set of initial fluid chemistry, the output was normalized into a non-dimensional ‘precipitation factor’ using a model run with modern (pre-industrial) seawater chemistry:

$$\text{Precipitation factor} = \frac{P}{P_{modern}} \quad (7)$$

Figure 3. Sensitivity analyses for box models. The surface water-kinetic model (a) is most sensitive to the starting Ω value while the porewater-equilibrium model (b) is most sensitive to alkalinity. c) Example of a Deffeyes diagram contoured by Ω for $[\text{Ca}^{2+}] = 10$ mmol/kgw. Data points show the range of Phanerozoic values from Ridgwell (2005). Note that the surface water-kinetic model depends only on Ω (i.e., the contour lines) but the porewater-equilibrium model depends on the spacing between the contour lines and the equilibrium line ($\Omega = 1$). For example, a marine fluid with $\Omega = 5$ and 2.5 mmol alkalinity (slightly higher than modern seawater) would need to precipitate ≈ 0.6 mmol of carbonate to reach equilibrium, but, a fluid with $\Omega = 5$ and 7.5 mmol alkalinity would need to precipitate more than twice as much carbonate (≈ 1.3 mmol), as denoted by the red arrows. See section 3.2 for further explanation

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3 Results

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3.1 Carbonate saturation states in modern evaporitic environments

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Brines in modern arid, carbonate producing environments show a wide range of saturation states (Fig. 2a) with mean values that differ between porewater and surface water environments (Welch's t-test, $p < 0.001$). The median aragonite saturation state for surface water samples ($\Omega = 8.3$) is higher than typical values for the surface ocean ($\Omega = 3-5$; Jiang et al., 2015) while the median saturation state of porewater samples ($\Omega = 2.8$) is lower than the parent water. This apparent contradiction arises because natural environments are open systems where the rate of fluid flow relative to mineral precipitation determines steady-state values of Ω . High saturation states occur when fluid residence times are short compared to the timescale of precipitation. This condition occurs in surface water environments such as tidal pools where brines are in close connection with marine parent fluids. In contrast, Wood et al. (2005) documented near-equilibrium between pore fluids and evaporite minerals in sabkha porewaters and attributed them to sluggish groundwater flow rates. We note, however, that there may be additional contributions from respired organic matter, although the total effect due to aerobic versus

Table 2. Statistical analysis of Phanerozoic data from arid coastal deposits, with number of occurrences (n) out of all deposits in the database (total). P-values are from Fisher’s exact test for independence. The compact letter display (CLD) shows statistically significant groupings as determined by a *post hoc* pairwise Fisher comparison. Entries marked with * are distinct from the youngest age group (mid-Jurassic to present).

Interval	All deposits	Tepees	No tepees	Tepee CLD	Pisoids	No pisoids	Pisoid CLD
Cambrian to Devonian	85	51	29	a*	6	74	a
Carboniferous to early Permian	23	4	19	b	3	20	ab
mid-Permian to early Jurassic	54	39	15	a*	20	34	b*
mid-Jurassic to present	80	15	70	b	4	81	a
total	242	109	103	p<0.001*	33	209	p<0.001*

255 anaerobic processes are still being investigated in modern settings (e.g., Ge et al., 2020).
 256 The overall differences in saturation states between surface water and porewater envi-
 257 ronments informed the use of two different endmembers in Section 2.3.

258 3.2 Sensitivity Analyses

259 Sensitivity analyses were performed to determine which inputs had the greatest ef-
 260 fect on precipitation rates. Both box models strongly depend on carbonate chemistry
 261 of the input solution, but are sensitive to different parameters (Fig. 3). The surface water-
 262 kinetic model is most sensitive to the saturation state of the starting fluid; higher start-
 263 ing saturations lead to higher steady state values during evaporation. The porewater-
 264 equilibrium model differs in that it is most sensitive to the the total alkalinity of the start-
 265 ing fluid. This alkalinity dependence can be visualized by plotting the input parameters
 266 on a Deffeyes diagram (Fig. 3c). For each parcel of fluid that enters the control volume,
 267 carbonates precipitate until the system achieves equilibrium (i.e., $\Omega = 1$). Precipitation
 268 removes alkalinity and total carbon in a 2:1 ratio so that all fluids follow a common tra-
 269 jectory represented by the vectors in Figure 3c. The length of the vectors—and by exten-
 270 sion, the amount of carbonate precipitated—depends on the spacing between Ω contours.
 271 The alkalinity dependence is shown by the diverging contours, which create longer vec-
 272 tor paths at higher alkalinity values. In contrast, changes in temperature and major ion
 273 composition (e.g., SO_4^{2-}) produce small effects compared to changes in carbonate chem-
 274 istry (Fig. 3 a, b). Overall, the models suggest that carbonate chemistry of the start-
 275 ing marine fluid can be a first-order control on carbonate precipitation rates in arid coastal
 276 settings, with alkalinity controlling porewater-equilibrium facies and saturation state con-
 277 trolling surface water-kinetic facies.

278 3.3 Model and data comparisons

279 Tepee and pisoid abundances show statistically significant changes through the Phanero-
 280 zoic (Fig. 4 a, b). Results from Fisher’s exact test of independence are sufficient to re-
 281 ject the null hypothesis that the proportions of preserved tepees and pisoids have not
 282 changed throughout the Phanerozoic (Table 2, p <0.001 for both). *Post-hoc* pairwise com-
 283 parisons identified specific intervals which have higher proportions of sedimentary struc-

Figure 4. Total abundances of tepee structures (a) and pisoids (b) binned by age. Bars are colored by the presence (blue for tepees and green for pisoids) or absence (grey) of features in each bin. Data were further grouped into four bins (separated by dashed lines) for statistical testing. Letters (a, b*, etc.) correspond to time periods with higher facies abundances than the youngest time bin (mid-Jurassic to present, see Table 2). The abrupt decline in tepee and pisoid facies coincides with the mid-Mesozoic Revolution. c) data on estimated extent of carbonate platforms throughout the Phanerozoic (grey boxes, Kiessling et al., 2003) and sea level (solid line, Haq et al., 1988). Also shown are reference trends for calcite/aragonite seas (Stanley & Hardie, 1998), tectonics (Crowley et al., 1998), and climate (warm in black bars, cool in white bars) (Bradley, 2011).

Figure 5. Relative abundances (%) of tepee structures (blue; a) and pisoids (green; b) binned by age. Data were further grouped into four bins (separated by dashed lines) with letters (a, b*, etc.) correspond to time periods with higher facies abundances than the youngest time bin (mid-Jurassic to present, see Table 2). The abrupt decline in tepee and pisoid facies coincides with the mid-Mesozoic Revolution. Box model results at 40°C are shown by solid black lines with shaded regions showing runs from 30-50°. The porewater-equilibrium model (a) fits the tepee data and the surface water-kinetic model (b) fits the pisoid data. Both model results are depicted as “precipitation factors” normalized to outputs from modern ocean chemistry. (c, d) Inputs for marine alkalinity and calcite saturation state taken from Ridgwell (2005). As suggested by the sensitivity analyses, the porewater-equilibrium and surface water-kinetic models can be treated as first-order functions of alkalinity and Ω respectively (Fig. 3a, b). The pattern of abundant tepees but rare pisoids of the early Paleozoic indicates an ocean with a large alkalinity reservoir but relatively low Ω . Reference trends for calcite/aragonite seas, tectonics, and climate are also shown (as in Fig. 4)

284 tures relative to the Middle Jurassic–present. Tepee data show relatively high abundances
 285 in the Cambrian–Devonian (60%) and Mid-Permian–Early Jurassic (70%) while pisoid
 286 abundances are only significantly higher in the Middle Permian–Early Jurassic (37%).
 287 Importantly, the abundances of the two facies types do not follow one another exactly,
 288 particularly in the early Paleozoic (Cambrian–Devonian) where tepees are abundant but
 289 pisoids are scarce. Note that the total deposits in each bin do not necessarily reflect the
 290 total extent of carbonate platforms throughout the Phanerozoic as estimated by Kiessling
 291 et al. (2003).

292 When the outputs from precipitation models are compared to relative abundances
 293 of facies, the porewater-equilibrium model matches tepee abundances while the surface
 294 water-kinetic model matches pisoid trends (Fig. 5). These results are consistent with process-
 295 based understanding of how these features form. The match between the surface water-
 296 kinetic model and pisoid abundances is consistent with evidence for subaqueous trans-
 297 port (i.e., grain breakages) in surface water environments. In contrast, tepees form through
 298 precipitation of cements in porewaters below the active transport layer, which is more
 299 consistent with porewater-equilibrium conditions associated with long fluid residence times.
 300 In turn, the sensitivity analyses (Section 4.3) suggest that each model can be approx-
 301 imated as functions of a single input variable. To a first order, tepee and pisoid abun-
 302 dances can be matched to Phanerozoic alkalinity and saturation state curves, respectively,
 303 as modeled by Ridgwell (2005) (Fig. 5c, d).

304 4 Discussion

305 4.1 Local versus global drivers

306 A key question about both the modeling and stratigraphic data approaches pre-
 307 sented here is whether they adequately capture global trends rather than local ones. One
 308 potential drawback is that the models assume similar local factors such as flow rates and
 309 reactive surface areas among all runs. The models are oversimplified in the sense that
 310 flow rates, grain size, and surface area will almost certainly vary between deposits and
 311 even laterally within the same system. In reality, arid coastal deposits often appear within
 312 multiple cycles at the scale of members and formations (e.g., Tinker, 1998) which likely
 313 captures a range of grain sizes and fluid flow rates. Since the stratigraphic database is
 314 binary (present/absent), the appearance of tepees and pisoids within any cycle or along
 315 strike counts as ‘present’ for the entire unit. It is likely that the coarse resolution of the
 316 database only serves to emphasize long-term regional or global trends rather than local
 317 ones. Furthermore, we are not aware of processes that would create large-scale, system-
 318 atic differences in average flow rate and/or particle size that could account for the statistically-
 319 significant results in Table 2. Overall, the correlations between model results and sur-
 320 veyed deposits support the hypothesis that arid coastal deposits are fundamentally tied
 321 to average global surface ocean chemistry.

322 4.2 Implications for Phanerozoic marine chemistry

323 The match between facies and marine carbonate chemistry can be used to test sev-
 324 eral hypotheses about the Phanerozoic carbon cycle developed from Earth systems mod-
 325 els. The largest drop in preserved tepee and pisoid facies coincides with a major radi-
 326 ation of pelagic calcifying organisms known as the mid-Mesozoic revolution (Martin, 1995;
 327 Ridgwell, 2005) (Fig. 4). This event has long been regarded as a major reorganization
 328 of the geologic carbon cycle that divides the Phanerozoic (Ridgwell, 2005; Grotzinger
 329 & Knoll, 1995; Zeebe & Westbroek, 2003). In the modern ocean, pelagic calcifiers are
 330 part of a negative-feedback mechanism that buffers the ocean against large changes in
 331 carbonate chemistry through deepening or shallowing of the carbonate compensation depth
 332 (Tyrrell & Zeebe, 2004; Zeebe et al., 2012). Earth systems models that explicitly incor-
 333 porate these feedbacks (e.g., Ridgwell 2005) predict that trends in alkalinity and Ω were

334 relatively stable after the mid-Mesozoic Revolution. The data corroborate this idea; since
 335 tepees and pisoids are rare in modern environments, their scarcity in deposits dating back
 336 to the mid-Jurassic is consistent with near-modern values of alkalinity and Ω .

337 In contrast, weaker carbonate buffering before the mid-Mesozoic should have per-
 338 mitted large changes in marine carbonate chemistry. In particular, most models of the
 339 pre-Mesozoic carbon cycle posit that Ω was inversely proportional to the area of sub-
 340 merged continental shelves and thus subject to long-term trends in sea level and tecton-
 341 ics (Grotzinger & Knoll, 1995; Zeebe & Westbroek, 2003). The model from Ridgwell (2005)
 342 uses the sea level curve of Haq et al. (1988) as a proxy for total shelf area; the maximum
 343 values for surface water Ω (Fig. 5d) coincide with the Phanerozoic minimum in sea level
 344 from the mid-Permian to mid-Jurassic (Fig. 4c). An independent estimate of carbonate
 345 platform area from Kiessling et al. (2003) shows similarly low values during this period
 346 (Fig. 4c). By the same logic, the maximum in relative pisoid abundance during the mid-
 347 Permian to mid-Jurassic (Fig. 5b) can be explained by a strong Ω dependence on shelf
 348 area. Interestingly, these trends do not appear to be strong functions of calcium concen-
 349 trations or weathering intensity, both of which also affect Ω . The maximum calcium con-
 350 centrations in Stanley and Hardie (1998) occur in the Cretaceous and earlier in the Pa-
 351 leozoic, bracketing the peak in pisoid abundance. For weathering intensity, (Ridgwell,
 352 2005) treated the alkalinity flux into the oceans as a constant prior to 230 Ma because
 353 no suitable constraints were available. The general shape of both the pisoids and mod-
 354 eled Ω curves cannot be attributed to changes in weathering intensity prior to 230 Ma.

355 Another important set of hypotheses pertain to the role of carbonate chemistry dur-
 356 ing the proliferation of biocalcifiers during the early Paleozoic. While some models of
 357 seawater chemistry predict near-modern Ω values for the early Paleozoic (Ridgwell, 2005),
 358 others predict extremely high values ($\Omega > 10$) for the same interval (Riding & Liang,
 359 2005; Arvidson et al., 2006). Studies that favor high Ω in the early Paleozoic (Riding &
 360 Liang, 2005) posit that declining saturation states partially explain why skeletal reefs
 361 replaced microbial ones over this time period (Kiessling, 2002), citing the influence of
 362 ambient Ω values on the preservation of cyanobacteria filaments (Arp et al., 2001). In
 363 contrast, other studies have argued that higher saturation states would have a greater
 364 effect on the abundance and diversity of skeletal metazoans (Knoll, 2003; Pruss et al.,
 365 2010). Higher saturation states reduce the cost of biocalcification, freeing up metabolic
 366 energy for use in other critical activities such as reproduction (Knoll, 2003). The grad-
 367 ual increase in skeletal content and diversity throughout the Cambrian-Ordovician might
 368 then represent an increase in Ω in the surface ocean rather than a decline (Pruss et al.,
 369 2010). The early decoupling of Paleozoic facies trends presented here are provide a use-
 370 ful baseline for these arguments as they indicate an ocean with a large alkalinity pool
 371 but Ω values that were similar to today in agreement with the Ridgwell (2005) model.
 372 In particular, the low abundances of pisoids in the early Paleozoic suggest that satura-
 373 tion states did not reach the same peaks ($\Omega > 10$) as the mid-Permian to mid-Jurassic.

374 4.3 Applications to shorter and longer timescales

375 In addition to constraining Phanerozoic-scale trends in alkalinity and Ω , data from
 376 arid coastal deposits could be applied at both shorter (< 1 my) and longer (Ga) timescales.
 377 Many carbon cycle perturbations such as the end-Permian extinction are associated with
 378 ocean acidification (low Ω) followed by the development of overlying non-skeletal facies
 379 (Baud et al., 2007). A high-resolution record of Ω and alkalinity proxies could help de-
 380 termine whether facies patterns represent an increase in surface-water alkalinity and Ω
 381 due to increased weathering after the event (Payne & Kump, 2007) or are instead related
 382 to alkalinity and Ω gradients driven by ocean anoxia (Higgins et al., 2009).

383 In deeper time, evaporitic environments are especially valuable proxies for carbon-
 384 ate chemistry because they do not rely on skeletal carbonates. As such, they could pro-

385 vide a reasonable bridge between the Phanerozoic and the Precambrian as far back as
 386 the Paleoproterozoic (Grotzinger, 1986) or even Archean (Hofmann et al., 2004). While
 387 Precambrian carbonate facies are often taken as evidence of extremely high surface Ω
 388 (Grotzinger & James, 2000), recent research has focused on the role of microbial metabolisms
 389 in localizing precipitation below the sediment-water interface (Bergmann et al., 2013;
 390 Higgins et al., 2009). Precambrian tepee and pisoid facies could also be related to Earth’s
 391 redox history (Knoll et al., 2016), and constraining ancient alkalinity would narrow the
 392 range of possible pH and pCO_2 values for early ocean-atmosphere systems (Isson & Planavsky,
 393 2018; Cantine et al., 2020). Using the Phanerozoic record as a guide, Precambrian records
 394 of these facies (e.g., Cantine et al., 2020) could greatly clarify the role of tectonics, cli-
 395 mate, and ocean chemistry during key transitions in early life.

396 5 Conclusions

397 Carbonates facies associated with arid coastal settings are common in the rock record.
 398 Although there are modern analogs for these systems, their facies composition has shifted
 399 through time, suggesting they may be related to long-term changes in marine environ-
 400 ments. Using a combination of stratigraphic data and geochemical forward modeling,
 401 we tie these facies trends to secular changes in the carbonate chemistry of seawater. Te-
 402 pee structures, which form when carbonate cements precipitate in near-surface porewa-
 403 ters, are sensitive to changes in the total alkalinity reservoir in seawater. In contrast, pisoids
 404 track the saturation state of carbonate minerals much like other coated grains. Both fea-
 405 tures were more common before the rapid expansion of pelagic calcifying organisms dur-
 406 ing the mid-Mesozoic; prior to this event, changes in sea level and carbonate shelf area
 407 exerted a much stronger control on ocean chemistry than they do today. We conclude
 408 that the relative abundances of tepee and pisoid facies are important physical proxies
 409 for marine carbonate chemistry, especially deeper in time when the marine carbon cy-
 410 cle was different from today. Importantly, these proxies do not rely on carbonate skele-
 411 tons, making them ideal for studying feedbacks between life and the carbon cycle either
 412 before the advent of animal biomineralization or during Phanerozoic extinction events.

413 Data

414 Data tabulated from the literature as well as any R scripts used for analysis and
 415 modeling are available as supplemental files and through and through a Github repos-
 416 itory (www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4408524).

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